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Affective norms of 875 Spanish words for five discrete emotional categories and two emotional dimensions

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Abstract

The current study presents affective norms for a new set of Spanish words that were scored on two emotional dimensions (valence and arousal) and in five discrete emotional categories (happiness, anger, sadness fear and disgust), as well as in concreteness, by 660 Spanish native speakers. Measures of several objective psycholinguistic variables – grammatical class, word frequency, number of letters and number of syllables- for the words were also included. We observed high split-half reliabilities for every emotional variable and a strong quadratic relationship between valence and arousal. Additional analyses revealed several associations between affective dimensions and discrete emotions, as well as with some psycholinguistics variables. This new corpus complements and extends prior databases in Spanish and allows designing new experiments investigating the influence of affective content in language processing under both dimensional and discrete theoretical conceptions of emotion. These norms can be downloaded as supplemental materials with this article.

Keywords: Emotion ratings; affective dimensions; discrete emotions; valence; arousal, concreteness; happy; angry; sad; fear; disgust

Introduction

A growing body of research indicates that emotional content modulates language comprehension and production (e.g., Citron, 2012; Herbert, Junghofer & Kissler, 2008; Hinojosa, Méndez-Bértolo, Carretié & Pozo, 2010; Kissler, Asadollahi & Herbert, 2006; Scott, O'Donnell & Sereno, 2012). These effects have been reported using a wide variety of methodologies, experimental paradigms and tasks. In this sense, differences in the processing of neutral and emotionally laden words have been found in behavioral, event-related potentials, functional magnetic resonance (fMRI) and positron emission tomography (PET) studies with a variety of tasks including lexical decision, emotional Stroop, emotional category judgments or silent reading (Dijksterhuis & Aarts, 2003; Estes & Verges, 2008; González-Villar, Triñanes, Zurrón & Carrillo de la Peña, 2014; Hinojosa, Méndez-Bértolo & Pozo, 2010b; Robinson, Storbek, Meier & Kirkeby, 2004; Schacht & Sommer, 2009; Straube, Sauer & Miltner, 2011). Typically, a processing advantage for emotional compared with neutral words is observed at several processing stages. In this sense, compared to neutral words emotional words seem to engage additional attentional resources that speed their processing (Hofmann, Kuchinke, Tamm, Vo & Jacobs, 2009; Kissler & Herbert, 2013; Kissler, Herbert, Peyk & Junghofer, 2007; Kousta, Vinson & Vigliocco, 2009; Méndez-Bértolo, Pozo & Hinojosa, 2011a). However, some studies reported slower recognition of negative compared to neutral and/or positive words (Algom, Chajut & Lev, 2004; Estes & Adelman, 2008; Estes & Verges, 2008; Kuperman, Estes, Brysbaert & Warriner, 2014). The processing of emotional words also modulates activity in several cortical and subcortical regions including the amygdala, as well as prefrontal and visual cortices (Isenberg, Silbersweig, Engelen, Emmerich, Malavade, Beattie, et al., 1999; Kuchinke, Jacobs, Grubich, Vo, Conrad & Herrmann, 2005; Nakic, Smith, Busis, Vythilingam &

Blair, 2006). Recently, there is evidence suggesting that emotional effects on word processing may also be observed in more complex linguistic contexts such as sentences or texts. For instance, it has been shown that emotional aspects of stories activate the amygdala and the ventromedial prefrontal cortex (Ferstl, Rinck, & von Cramon, 2005). Also, affective content modulates agreement relations between the constituents of a sentence, attachment decisions on relative clauses and lexico-semantic processes related to word meaning integration in sentences (Fraga, Piñeiro, Acuña-Fariña, Redondo & García-Orza, 2012; Hinojosa, Albert, Fernández-Folgueiras, Santaniello, López-Bachiller, Sebastián et al., 2014; Holt, Lynn & Kuperberg, 2009; Martín-Loeches, Fernández, Schacht, Sommer, Casado, Jiménez-Ortega et al., 2012).

Two main theoretical approaches have been proposed to best characterize emotions, each receiving empirical support, namely the two-dimensional circumplex model and the discrete emotion theory. The two-dimensional circumplex model claims that emotions arise from two independent neurophysiological systems (Barrett & Russell, 1999; Russell, 1980, 2003). The dimension of valence ranges from pleasant to unpleasant, whereas the dimension of arousal describes the degree of activation from calming to exciting. From a different perspective, the so-called discrete emotion theories assume that all emotions can be derived from a limited number of innate and universal affective states such as happiness, anger, sadness, fear and disgust (Ekman, 1992, 1999; Panksepp, 1998). Accordingly, independent neural mechanisms would underlie every discrete basic emotion. Although this framework has been extensively investigated in studies that explored the processing of facial expressions (e.g., Eimer & Holmes, 2002; Eimer, Holmes & McGlone, 2003), the discrete emotion approach has received relatively less attention in language research. However, there is some evidence pointing to the existence of categorical effects in the processing of emotional words. In

this direction, the results of several studies revealed shorter lexical decision times for happy words compared to both fearful and neutral words (Briesemeister, Kuchinke & Jacobs, 2011a, b). Therefore, some authors have suggested that additional efforts are needed with combined approaches to conduct experiments that provide with a more comprehensive view of emotional effects on word processing (Brisemeister, Kuchinke & Jacobs, 2011b; Stevenson, Mikels & James, 2007).

Research concerning the effects of emotional content on language processing has used words from norm lists. For instance, the Affective Norms for English words (ANEW; Bradley & Lang, 1999), which provides ratings for 1034 words in the dimensions of valence, arousal and dominance, is the most widely used corpus in English. This corpus has been adapted to several languages including Spanish (Redondo, Fraga, Padrón & Comesaña, 2007), European Portuguese (Soares, Comesaña, Pinheiro, Simoes & Frade, 2012) or Italian (Montefinese, Ambrosini, Fairfield & Mammarella, 2014). Furthermore, as Table 1 shows, other databases also exist in different languages, such as English (Warriner, Kuperman & Brysbaert, 2013), French (Monnier & Syssau, 2013), German (Vo, Jacobs & Conrad, 2006) or Dutch (Moors, De Houwer, Hermans, Wanmaker, van Schie, Van Harmelen et al., 2013).

Five Spanish-language databases are currently available with affective scores for words. The first was published by Campos and Astorga (1989). It included 300 words rated by 100 young adults in pleasantness (on a 9-point scale) and abstractness (on a 7-point scale). Redondo, Fraga, Comesaña and Perea (2005) drew up another affective database of 478 words that were rated by 360 participants in valence and arousal with the Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM; Bradley & Lang, 1994). This study also provided scores taken from the LEXEP (Sebastián-Galles, Martí, Carreiras, & Cuetos, 2000) in several subjective psycholinguistic variables whenever they were available, including

familiarity, concreteness and imaginability. A third database, was an Spanish adaptation of the ANEW (Redondo et al., 2007). Using the SAM, ratings for valence, arousal and dominance were collected for 1034 words in 720 young adults. Again, scores for familiarity, concreteness and imaginability were taken from the LEXEP. A fourth database, compiled by Pérez-Dueñas, Acosta, Mejías and Lupiáñez (2010), provides ratings for 238 nouns. These words were assessed by 252 participants for valence (on a 9-point scale ranging from -5 *very negative* to 5 *very positive*), arousal (on a 10-point scale), as well as relevance for anxiety, depression and anger (also on a 10-point scale). Finally, Ferré, Guash, Moldovan and Sánchez-Casas (2012), reported ratings from 504 participants for valence and arousal (using the SAM), as well as for familiarity and concreteness (on a 9-point scale). Scores were collected for 380 words belonging to the semantic categories of animals, objects and people.

These databases have proven to be invaluable for researches interested in affective language. Nonetheless, as experimental evidence has accumulated, new corpora are needed that include those modulating variables not considered in current norm lists. This will allow to further extend our knowledge about the mechanisms involved in the processing of affective content in linguistic stimuli. Our main aim was therefore to generate a database of Spanish words suitable for investigating effects of emotional features in language processing. We collected affective norms for a new set of Spanish words that were not included in prior Spanish databases by Redondo and collaborators (2007) or Ferré, Guash, Moldovan and Sánchez-Casas (2012). Thus, our corpus also provides additional materials that may be useful when researches could not find enough stimuli in the current available databases in order to prevent possible effects of word repetition (Ferré et al., 2012).

In addition, we also aimed at complementing previous databases in several methodological and theoretical aspects. First, words were rated in the two main affective dimensions (valence and arousal), as well as in five discrete emotional categories (happiness, anger, sadness, fear and disgust). As we have already mentioned, in the light of recent evidence suggesting a role of discrete emotions in word processing (Briesemeister et al., 2011a, b; Briesemeister, Kuchinke & Jacobs, 2014; Silva, Montant, Ponz & Ziegler, 2012), studies using emotional words as stimuli would benefit not only from a dimensional but also from a categorical characterization of words. Norms for discrete emotions, however, are not yet available in Spanish (for norms in German, see Briesemeister et al., 2011b; for norms in English, see Stevenson et al., 2007, and Strauss & Allen, 2008; see also Stevenson & James, 2008, for ratings on discrete emotional categories for the International Affective Digitized Sounds).

Second, some reports observed that grammatical word class influence emotion effects in word comprehension, with a processing advantage for emotional nouns and adjectives compared to verbs (Palazova, Mantwill, Sommer & Schacht, 2011; Schacht & Sommer, 2009). These findings suggest that additional research is needed that explores the role of grammatical category in relation to other variables impacting the processing of affective content. However, some published norm lists in Spanish included only nouns (Ferré et al., 2012), or less than 10% of verbs (Redondo et al., 2007). In the current corpus we report ratings from 304 verbs (34.7%), 301 nouns (34.4%), 126 adjectives (14.4%) and 144 words that could be considered both as an adjective and a noun (16.5%). Thus, we provide a set of stimuli that could be suitable to further explore word class effects on the processing of emotional words.

Third, accumulating evidence suggests that emotion content is a crucial variable in the representation of abstract concepts. In these sense, it has been reported that

emotional content may exert a greater influence in the processing of abstract compared to concrete words (Hinojosa, Albert, López-Martín & Carretié, 2014; Kanske & Kotz, 2007; Kousta, Vigliocco, Vinson, Andrews & Del Campo, 2011; Palazova, Sommer & Schacht, 2013; Vigliocco, Kousta, Della Rosa, Vinson, Tettamanti, Devlin et al., 2013). Thus, given the importance of this variable participants rated every word in the concreteness dimension. This would complement previous norm lists in which concreteness values for 380 nouns were collected (Ferré et al., 2012), or just reported concreteness ratings for a subset of words (Redondo et al., 2007). In addition, frequency of use taken from LEXEP (Sebastián-Gallés et al., 2000), and word-length (number of letters and syllables) were reported.

Method

Participants

Values from 660 native Spanish participants (507 females, 153 males; mean age = 23.2 years, *S.D.* = 7.2) were collected. Most of them were students from three universities of Madrid (Complutense University, Autónoma University and Rey Juan Carlos I University), but several non-student participants also participated in the study. The sample included volunteer participants from different levels of educational attainment: high school degree (15.6%), undergraduate studies (67.7%), graduate studies (9.4%) and doctorate (7.7%).

Materials and procedure

The word set contained 875 Spanish words. Words were selected from the LEXEP (Sebastián-Galles et al., 2001) and prior studies by our group (Hinojosa et al., 2010b; Hinojosa, Carretié, Valcárcel, Méndez-Bértolo & Pozo, 2009; Hinojosa, Méndez-Bértolo Pozo, 2012; Hinojosa, Mercado, Albert, Barjola, Peláez, Villalba-García & Carretié, 2015; Méndez-Bértolo, Pozo & Hinojosa, 2011b). The selection of the words

attempted to include as many words as possible with a marked affective value in addition to neutral words. The only constraint was that these words were not included in the Spanish Adaptation of the ANEW (Redondo et al., 2007) or in the database by Ferré and collaborators (2012), with the exception of 16 and 11 words, respectively. Although one of our main purposes was to collect norms for a new set of words, this procedure would allow testing reliability of scores for a small set of words across studies. The whole 875-word set was divided into 21 lists of 40 words and one list of 35 words. It was decided to use an online survey procedure, owing to the benefits that it brings in speed and wideness of distribution (Couper, 2000). The surveys were created using a professional account of the SurveyMonkey web software. The URL links were randomly distributed among our sample. Ratings from 30 participants were collected for each word in every list.

Upon accessing the questionnaire, participants found an initial page in which they answered a few demographic questions (age, sex, and level of educational attainment). Every effort was made to provide here clear filling instructions. In this sense, instructions for valence, arousal and concreteness ratings were an adaptation of those used in a prior study by Ferré and collaborators (2012) and the procedure used in Stevenson and collaborators' study (2007) was adapted for discrete categories. These instructions are presented in the Appendix. Participants were informed about the time estimated for completion (which was about 20-25 min), as well as a statement about data confidentiality and about the purposes of the research. We also provided an email contact in case they had any questions or would like to request more details about our research (as was suggested in Burke & James, 2006). Finally, they were informed that there were no right or wrong answers and encouraged not to think a lot about their ratings.

The following two pages contained each the list of 40 words, presented at the center of the screen, using a Helvetica 14-point bold Font. In one of the pages, the valence, arousal and concreteness 9-point scales were presented under each word, as in several studies published in this field (e.g., Ferré et al., 2012; Redondo et al., 2007; Vo et al., 2006). In the other page, the five basic emotions (happiness, anger, sadness, fear, and disgust) were presented on a 5-point scale below each word, with 1 being *not at all* and 5 being *extremely* (Stevenson et al., 2007). Five-point scales have been used in previous studies that collected word scores for discrete dimensions in either English (Stevenson et al., 2007) or German (Brisemeister et al., 2011b). For each word, we provided a response option labeled “I don’t know the meaning” (mean responses per word = 0.25, *s.d.* = 1.07).

It is worth noting that the order of presentation of words in each page, the order of the scales for each word in a given questioner, as well as the order of appearance of the two word-rating pages was randomized in all of the questionnaires. Furthermore, it was set that once the answers to a page had been submitted, participants could not go back to change their ratings. Each page began with a header that included clear instructions to the rating scales in that page. In the case of the scales of valence and arousal, such instructions included the pictorial depiction of the SAM. The SAM is a widely used tool in the assessment of affective properties of stimuli. For the valence dimension, the SAM ranges from a smiling to a frowning figure, while it ranges from an excited to a relaxed figure for the arousal dimension (Bradley & Lang, 1994).

Results and discussion

Table 2 shows a general overview of the database, with descriptive statistics for valence, arousal, concreteness, as well as those for each of the five discrete emotions and the psycholinguistic variables. The word list resulting from the rating procedure can

be accessed as supplemental material <https://www.dropbox.com/s/o6dpw3irk6utfhy/Hinojosa%20et%20al%20Supplementary%20materials.xlsx?dl=0>

We first explore the reliability of the ratings in every affective dimension and discrete emotion, as well as in concreteness scores. Thereafter, we report our analyses of the associations between valence and arousal ratings, and between affective dimensions and discrete emotions. Finally, the relationship between affective variables and psycholinguistic characteristics included in our database is considered.

Reliability

The reliability of the ratings in all the variables that were included in the database was estimated by using the split-half intergroup procedure. For each version of the questionnaire participants were randomly divided into two subgroups of equal size. Pearson correlations were calculated between participants' ratings for the two affective dimensions (i. e., valence and arousal), the five discrete emotions (i.e., happiness, anger, sadness, fear, and disgust), and the concrete dimension. The corrected correlations using the Spearman-Brown formula were positive and highly significant. For emotional dimensions, mean correlation values were $r = .89$ for arousal (ranging from $r = .73$ to $r = .99$) and $r = .94$ for valence (ranging from $r = .77$ to $r = .99$). This finding agrees with previous reports that showed greater variability for arousal than for valence scores (Eilola & Havelka, 2010; Monnier & Syssau, 2014; Moors et al., 2013; Redondo et al., 2007). High correlations were also observed for discrete emotions, with mean values of $r = .97$ for happiness (ranging from $r = .88$ to $r = .99$), $r = .97$ for anger (ranging from $r = .95$ to $r = .99$), $r = .97$ for sadness (ranging from $r = .92$ to $r = .99$), $r = .96$ for fear (ranging from $r = .90$ to $r = .99$) and $r = .96$ for disgust (ranging from $r = .90$ to $r = .98$). Thus, variability was greater when participants had to score affective dimensions than

when they were instructed to rate discrete emotions, with only subtle differences existing among discrete emotion categories. Finally, we found a strong correlation for concreteness, with mean $r = .88$ (ranging from $r = .76$ to $r = .95$).

To further examine the generalizability of our ratings in affective dimensions (there are no prior ratings for discrete emotions in Spanish), we correlated them with scores from previous studies. There were 16 words in common with Redondo and collaborators (2007) and 11 words that were previously scored in Ferré and co-workers' (2012) study. For the valence dimension a strong correlation was found ($r = .99$, with Redondo et al., 2007; $r = .98$, with Ferré et al., 2012). Also a high positive correlation was observed for the arousal dimension ($r = .98$, with Redondo et al., 2007; $r = .74$, with Ferré et al., 2012). Thus, it seems likely that the norms collected in the current study may generalize to those obtained in previous work and are suitable to be used for the selection of stimuli in language and affective research.

Relationship between the valence and arousal dimensions

As in previous studies, we carried out regressions analyses with Emotional Valence as the independent factor and Arousal as the dependent factor (e.g., Ferré et al., 2012; Monnier & Syssau, 2014). The linear and quadratic models were tested separately. A high quadratic relation between valence and arousal was observed, $R = .57$, $F(2,872) = 205.75$, $p < .0001$, with the quadratic relation accounting for 32.1% of the variance. The quadratic model outperformed the simpler linear model, which, although significant, explained only 2.3% of the variance [$R = .16$, $F(2,873) = 20.2$, $p < .0001$].

Figure 1 shows the location of the 875 words ratings in the two-dimensional affective space. In line with the findings of prior studies providing emotional ratings for words in different languages, the boomerang-shaped distribution observed in Figure 1 indicated that highly pleasant and unpleasant words were rated as being the most arousing stimuli

whereas items with low positive and negative ratings were perceived to be the least arousing (Bradley & Lang, 1999; Eilola & Havelka, 2010; Ferré et al., 2012; Kanske & Kotz, 2010; Monnier & Syssau, 2014; Montefinese et al., 2014; Redondo et al., 2007; Soares et al.; 2012; Vo et al., 2009).

The association between valence and arousal was further examined by classifying each of the words in the database as being positive, negative or neutral. Items were distributed according to the same criteria used in prior studies (Ferré et al., 2012; Monnier & Sussau, 2014). Thus, words with values of valence ranging from 1 to 4 were considered as negative ($M = 2.37$, $S.D. = 0.73$), words scored between 4 and 6 were classified as neutral ($M = 4.93$, $S.D. = 0.51$), and words ranging from 6 to 9 were considered as positive ($M = 7.29$, $S.D. = 0.67$). According to this procedure, we identified 337 negative (38.43% of the corpus; e.g. “ansiedad”, *anxiety*), 231 neutral (38.43%; e.g. “recolectar”, *to collect*) and 307 positive (35.12%; “divertido”, *funny*) words. Thereafter, we explored the relation between the valence and arousal scores for the negative and positive words taken separately. A significant negative correlation between valence and arousal was observed for negative words ($r = -.37$, $p < .0001$), indicating that the most negative words were also those with highest ratings in the arousal dimension (e.g. “disparar”, *to fire*). Regarding positive words, we found a significant positive correlation ($r = .25$, $p < .0001$) suggesting that the most positive words were also the most arousing (e.g. “besar”, *to kiss*). These findings agree with previous reports (e.g. Monnier & Syssau, 2014; Schmidtke, Schröder, Jacobs & Conrad, 2014). However, in the current study the correlation between valence and arousal showed a steeper slope for negative compared to positive words. Thus, we contrasted arousal scores for negative and positive words with a t test and found that they were different [$t(306) = -4.37$, $p < .0001$]. In agreement with prior research (e.g., Citron,

Weekes & Ferstl, 2014; Ferré et al., 2012), this result reflects the fact that positive words were more distributed around the arousal dimension (range: 1.87-8.29, $M = 5.75$, $S.D. = 1.26$) than negative words (range: 2.77-8.27, $M = 6.15$, $S.D. = 1.02$). As has been suggested, positive stimuli are associated with feeling of safety so they are not necessarily high in arousal (e.g., *peace, relax*), whereas negative stimuli may reflect a dangerous event that requires a quick response (Citron et al., 2014; Lang, Bradley & Cuthbert, 1990)

Relationship between affective dimensions and discrete emotions

Additionally, we carried out general correlational analyses with the discrete emotion scores and ratings in the valence and arousal dimensions for every word. Given the high number of comparisons we tested (i.e., 55), we reported results that were significant at the Bonferroni-corrected α value of $.05/55 \approx .0009$ (see Montefinese et al., 2014, for a similar procedure). Table 3 shows the results of these analyses. In line with prior reports, we observed a highly significant positive correlation between each of the four negative emotional categories and arousal, as well as between scores in happiness and valence. Negative correlations existed between negative discrete emotions and valence, and between happiness and the other emotional categories.

Additional analyses were conducted to further investigate the relationships between affective dimensions and discrete emotions. These analyses were limited to words with scores higher than 2.5 in a given emotional category, which were classified as denoting either happy ($M = 3.8$, $S.D. = 0.59$), angry ($M = 3.71$, $S.D. = 0.56$), sad ($M = 3.79$, $S.D. = 0.59$), fear ($M = 3.81$, $S.D. = 0.58$) or disgusting ($M = 3.80$, $S.D. = 0.67$) emotions. Those words with ratings higher than 2.5 in more than one emotional category (95 words, 10.85%: 40 words, 4.57%, in two categories; 31 words, 3.54%, in three categories; 24 words, 2.74%, in four categories), were ascribed to the category

with the highest score. This resulted in 307 words being associated with happy (35.1% of the database; e.g., “*infancia*”, *childhood*), 84 words with angry (9.6%; e.g., “*furia*”, *fury*), 87 with sad (9.9%; e.g., “*fallecer*”, *to perish*), 114 with fearful (13%; e.g., “*abismo*”, *abyss*), and 30 with disgusting (3.4%; e.g., “*repulsivo*” *repulsive*) concepts. As is shown in Table 4, ratings for those words belonging to each of the five discrete emotions showed positive significant correlations with their scores in arousal whereas ratings for angry, sad, fearful and disgusting words showed negative significant correlations with their ratings in the valence variable. Also, scores for words denoting happy concepts showed a positive correlation with their valence scores. These findings suggest a close relationship between ratings in affective dimensions and emotional discrete categories.

Overall, these results highlight the importance of considering ratings in both affective dimensions and categories when designing experiments, as they allow researchers to explore language in relation to both basic emotion and dimensional models (Strauss & Allen, 2008). In this sense, it has been argued that whereas a dimensional approximation can portray broad features of emotion, and the categorical perspective can capture more discrete emotional aspects, both views can be used in combination to draw a comprehensive picture of affective language processing (Stevenson et al., 2007).

Relationship between affective and psycholinguistic variables

Pearson correlations were calculated between subjective and objective psycholinguistic variables -frequency, word length (both number of letters and number of syllables), concreteness-, and emotional variables (see Table 4). Concreteness scores showed significant positive correlations with ratings in arousal, indicating that more arousing words were rated as more concrete. In contrast, a significant negative correlation between valence and concreteness scores was observed, suggesting that words rated as

more positive were also rated as more abstract (e.g. “creativo”, *creative*). Also, ratings in anger, sadness, fear and disgust showed highly significant correlations with concreteness scores, although no significant correlations were found between scores in happiness and ratings in concreteness. These findings highlight the importance of taking into consideration the modulatory role of concreteness on the processing of emotional words, which have been previously found to be of particular relevance in the case of abstract concepts (Kousta et al., 2011; Palazova et al., 2013; Yao & Wang, 2014).

Word frequency had a positive correlation with valence and happiness, and a negative correlation with arousal, anger, sadness, fear and disgust. Thus, words denoting positive concepts were those showing higher frequency values (e.g. “cine”, *cinema*). In contrast, high arousing words and those associated with negative discrete emotions showed lower frequency values. Again, the results of several studies underline the importance of controlling word frequency effects in studies dealing with the processing of emotional words. In this direction, interactions between word frequency and valence have been observed, especially during the processing of low-frequency negative words (Méndez-Bértolo et al., 2011a; Scott, O’Donnell, Leuthold & Sereno, 2009; Scott, O’Donnell & Sereno, 2014).

Finally, word length (measured in both number of letters and number of syllables) showed a positive correlation with arousal. The number of letters had also a positive correlation with angry, sad and fearful words. This means that longer words were rated as more activating and as being associated to angrier, sadder and more fearful concepts.

In summary, concerning discrete emotions, happy words showed higher frequency of use values, whereas angry, sad and fearful words had more letters, were more concrete and less frequent. Also, disgusting words were less frequent and more

concrete. Regarding affective dimensions, positive words were quite frequent and more abstract, whereas high arousing words were less frequent, longer and more concrete. Some of the patterns of correlations that we observed between affective dimensions and psycholinguistic variables matched previous findings (e.g., Citron et al., 2014; Gilet, Grünh, Studer & Labouvie-Vief, 2012; Monnier & Syssau, 2014; Vo et al., 2009; Warriner et al., 2013), whereas they were incompatible in some aspects with those reported in other studies (e.g., Ferré et al., 2012; Moors et al., 2013). Divergences can be attributed to differences in stimulus sets, language characteristics and/or sample peculiarities. Nevertheless, results from the current and other studies indicate that psycholinguistic variables should receive full consideration when designing investigations that manipulate affective variables with linguistic materials. This may be of particular interest for those studies investigating the processing of affective words from a discrete emotion perspective since there are no prior reports of a relationship between emotional categories and psycholinguistic variables such as concreteness or word frequency.

Gender differences

In order to explore the existence of gender differences in word ratings for both emotional dimensions and categories, we examined the associations between males' and females' scores. High correlations were found between men and women for the arousal ($r = .66$) and the valence ($r = .83$) dimensions (all $ps < .001$). Also, the ratings of men and women were highly correlated for the happy ($r = .90$), angry ($r = .83$), sad ($r = .77$), fear ($r = .81$) and disgust ($r = .80$) emotional categories (all $ps < .001$). These findings suggest that males and females closely agreed when they scored the words in both dimensional and discrete emotions, which resemble prior reports in the literature (e.g., Redondo et al., 2007; Monnier & Syssau, 2014; Soares et al., 2012).

We conducted additional analyses to compare the average emotional ratings by men and women participants by means of two-tailed paired t tests. Regarding affective dimensions, it was found that males gave higher mean valence scores than females [$M_s = 4.90$ and 4.78 , $SD_s = 2.17$ and 2.20 , respectively; $t(874) = -2.78$, $p < .01$], indicating that men assessed words as more positive than did women. This finding parallels those results reported in some studies (e.g., Monnier & Syssau, 2014; Montefinnesse et al., 2014; Soares et al., 2012), whereas it contradicts the results of other studies (Bradley & Lang, 1999; Redondo et al., 2007). Gender differences in valence ratings may be attributed to the existence of cognitive differences between the sexes or differences in response style (Belleza et al., 1986), although the inconsistency of prior reports suggest that some caution is needed when interpreting gender differences in affective word ratings. The same line of reasoning may be applied to the analysis of arousal scores. In line with prior reports (e.g., Gilet et al., 2012; Redondo et al., 2007), we found no differences between males' and females' ratings for the arousal dimension [$M_s = 5.52$ and 5.60 , $SD_s = 1.49$ and 2.17 , respectively; $t(874) = 1.84$, $p > .05$]. However, higher mean arousal ratings have been observed in some studies (e.g., Soares et al., 2012; Söderholm et al., 2013).

With respect to discrete categories, men reported significantly higher ratings for anger [$M_s = 1.91$ and 1.86 , $SD_s = 0.99$ and 0.97 , respectively; $t(874) = -2.32$, $p < .05$] and fear [$M_s = 2.12$ and 2.06 , $SD_s = 0.98$ and 1.00 , respectively; $t(874) = -3.16$, $p < .01$], while we did not observed differences between males and females for happiness [$M_s = 2.28$ and 2.26 , $SD_s = 1.25$ and 1.25 , respectively; $t(874) = -0.89$, $p > .05$], sadness [$M_s = 1.99$ and 1.95 , $SD_s = 0.98$ and 0.99 , respectively; $t(874) = -1.82$, $p > .05$] or disgust [$M_s = 1.70$ and 1.70 , $SD_s = 0.80$ and 0.82 , respectively; $t(874) = -0.55$, $p > .05$]. Although gender effects on words belonging to distinct discrete emotional categories have not

been previously explored, current data suggest that differences between men and women are noticeable in those negative emotional categories –anger and fear- which elicit rapid social/affective reactions (as compared to sadness or disgust categories). Taken together our findings show that some gender differences in the assessment of affective words exist at both dimensional and discrete emotions levels. This is in agreement with prior findings using a variety of experimental paradigms, which point to the existence of differences in the processing of emotional language between men and women (e.g., Hamann & Canli, 2004; Smith & Waterman, 2005). However, the high consistency between males' and females' affective ratings also suggests that the emotional experience of men and women is quite analogous, at least in several aspects.

Conclusions

Norm lists in which words are rated according to discrete emotions are not common, and those characterized along both discrete emotions and emotional dimensions are rare. At the present time, such corpora were only available in English (Stevenson et al., 2007; Strauss & Allen, 2008) and German (Briesemeister et al., 2011b). In the current study we provided additional data from a set of 875 Spanish words, allowing researchers to control their stimuli with regard to discrete and dimensional affective variables. Thus, our database may be a suitable tool to investigate interactions between dimensional and discrete emotion information. This may be especially relevant for theoretical proposals which pursue the objective of integrating discrete and dimensional conceptions into a unified theoretical approach (e.g., the *core affect theory*, Russell, 2003; see also Panksepp & Watt, 2011, for an alternative integrative account). In this direction, there is recent behavioral and ERPs evidence suggesting that discrete emotions may serve as a basis for subsequent dimensional appraisal processes alone (Briesemeister, Kuchinke & Jacobs, 2014), a finding that cannot easily be interpreted in terms of traditional discrete

emotion or affective dimension theories. As has been pointed out, “more research will have to be done to fully understand the interplay of the various dimensions constituting the affective space within and across different languages” (cf. Schmidtke et al., 2014, p.7). These additional efforts may benefit from norm lists providing stimuli rated in several emotional variables and in other languages in which they were not currently available, as is the case of the present database.

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Figure legends

Figure 1. Distribution of scores for the 875 words in the affective space defined by valence and arousal, for the total sample.

Figure 1

Table 1

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Study	Language	Number of Words	Emotional Variables	Psycholinguistic Subjective Variables	Grammatical Categories	Observations
Bauer & Ahuvia, 2008	English	144	Emotionality	Concreteness, imaginability, context availability	Nouns, adjectives, nouns/verbs, adjectives/verbs	
Beilza et al., 1986	English	399	Plausiveness	Familiarity, imagery	Not available	5-point scales.
Berckel, Kolarik, & Mornia, 2009	French	80	Valence, arousal	Not available	Not available	Spoken stimuli; 7-point scales.
Bradley & Lang, 1999	English	1,034	Valence, arousal, dominance	None	Nouns, verbs, adjectives	
Brascheimer et al., 2011b	German	1,958	Happiness, anger, fear, sadness, disgust	None	Nouns	
Campos & Astorga, 1988	Spanish	300	Plausiveness	Abstrateness	Not available	7-point scale for abstractness.
Caron et al., 2014	English	300	Valence, arousal	Familiarity, imaginability, age of acquisition	Nouns, verbs, adjectives, verbs/nouns	7-point scales.
Ehola & Havelka, 2010	Finnish and British English	210	Valence, emotional change	Concreteness, familiarity	Nouns	Offensiveness ratings; comparison with British English.
Ferré et al., 2012	Spanish	380	Valence, arousal	Concreteness, familiarity	Nouns	
Gil et al., 2012	French	853	Valence, arousal	Imagery	Adjectives	7-point scales; comparison young middle old adults.
Grahn & Smith, 2008	German	200	Valence, arousal, control	Imagery	Adjectives	Self-relevance, age relevance and self-offer relevance ratings; comparison young and older adults.
Janschowitz, 2008	English	460	Valence, arousal	Familiarity, imaginability	Nouns, verbs, adjectives	Personal use, offensiveness, taboonness ratings.
Karate & Koz, 2010	German	1,000	Valence, arousal	Concreteness	Nouns	Adaptation of ANEW.
Kaisensen, Gomes, Juno, & Vieira, 2011	Portuguese (Brazilian)	1,046	Valence, arousal	None	Nouns, verbs, adjectives	
Mormier & Syrett, 2014	French	1,031	Valence, arousal	None	Nouns, adjectives	
Montefinese et al., 2014	Italian	1,121	Valence, arousal, dominance	Concreteness, familiarity, imaginability	Nouns, verbs, adjectives, adjectives/nouns	Adaptation of ANEW.
Moors et al., 2013	Dutch	4,300	Valence, arousal, dominance	Age of acquisition	Nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs	7-point scales.
Nézet-Darlas et al., 2010	Spanish	238	Valence, arousal	Subjective frequency of use	Nouns	Relevance for anxiety, depression and anger (10-point scale); 10-point-scale for arousal.
Redondo et al., 2006	Spanish	478	Valence, arousal	None	Nouns	
Redondo et al., 2007	Spanish	1,034	Valence, arousal, dominance	Concreteness, familiarity, imaginability	Nouns, verbs, adjectives	Adaptation of ANEW.
Schmidtke et al., 2014	German	1,003	Valence, arousal (9- and 5-point scales), dominance	None	Nouns, verbs, adjectives	Adaptation of ANEW.

Table 2

Mean	4.77	5.52	2.29	1.92	2.02	2.14	1.72	6.03	20.78	7.64	3.17
<i>SD</i>	1.49	1.96	0.82	0.85	0.90	0.97	0.82	2.04	45.76	1.99	0.87
Minimum	1.1	1.73	1	1	1	1	1	2.07	0.18	2	1
Maximum	8.67	8.29	4.97	4.83	4.93	4.7	4.77	8.67	487.27	14	6
Range	7.57	6.56	3.97	3.83	3.93	3.7	3.77	6.6	487.1	12	5

Table 3

	Val	Aro	Con	Hap	Ang	Sad	Fea	Dis	Freq	Lett	Syll
Valence	1										
Arousal	-.15**	1									
Concreteness	-.11**	.14**	1								
Happiness	.93**	.07	-.04	1							
Anger	-.81**	.46**	.14**	-.64**	1						
Sadness	-.79**	.33**	.19**	-.62**	.33	1					
Fear	-.73**	.53**	.17**	-.57**	.77**	.81**	1				
Disgust	-.75**	.33**	.25**	-.60**	.76**	.63**	.60**	1			
Frequency	.15**	-.13**	-.17	.13**	-.15**	-.10*	-.10*	-.13**	1		
Length (letters)	-.07	.14**	-.04	-.05	.11**	.12**	.11*	.07	-.28**	1	
Length (syllables)	-.07	.10*	-.04	-.05	.08	.08	.07	.08	-.26**	.84**	1

* $p < .005$, ** $p < .001$

Table 4

	Happy	Angry	Sad	Fearful	Disgusting
Arousal	.48**	.67**	.35**	.57**	-.76**
Valence	.86**	-.73**	-.57**	-.70**	.51*

* $p < .005$, ** $p < .001$

APPENDIX

The following texts are the instructions given to the subjects, with their corresponding English translation:

- General instructions:

A continuación se presenta un listado de palabras en el que te pedimos que por favor las evalúes según una serie de criterios:

- *El grado de abstracción/concreción se refiere a cómo te resulta de abstracto o concreto el concepto al que se refiere cada palabra. Por ejemplo, “libertad” es un concepto abstracto, mientras que “vaso” es un concepto concreto.*
- *La activación hace referencia al nivel de relajación/activación que genera una palabra.*
- *La valencia es el grado en el que el concepto que designa una palabra hace referencia algo que te resulta negativo (aversivo) o positivo (atractivo).*
- *Por último, te pedimos que puntúes cada una de las palabras en las 5 categorías emocionales que se presentan (alegría, ira, tristeza, miedo, asco).*

Selecciona sólo una respuesta por cada palabra y recuerda que no hay respuestas correctas o incorrectas.

You will be presented with a list of words. We kindly ask you to rate them according to the following criteria:

- The level of abstraction/concreteness refers to how abstract or concrete you think that the concept is. For example, “freedom” is an abstract concept, while “glass” is a concrete one.
- Arousal refers to the level of relaxation/excitation that the word generates.
- Valence is the degree in which the concept expressed by the word refers to something

negative (aversive) or positive (attractive).

- Finally, we ask you to score each word in the 5 emotional categories given (happiness, anger, sadness, fear, disgust).

Choose only one answer for each word and remember that there are no right or wrong answers.

- Instructions for the dimensional ratings:

A continuación te pedimos que por favor nos indiques el nivel de valencia, activación y abstracción / concreción de los conceptos a los que hacen referencia las siguientes palabras.

La valencia es el grado en el que el concepto que designa una palabra hace referencia algo que te resulta negativo (aversivo) o positivo (atractivo). Valora las palabras en una escala del 1 al 9, siendo 1 "muy negativo" y 9 "muy positivo". Este dibujo es una representación de la escala.

La activación hace referencia al nivel de relajación/activación que genera una palabra. Usa una escala del 1 al 9, siendo 1 "muy poca activación" (algo muy relajante) y 9 "muchísima activación" (el máximo valor de activación generada). Este dibujo es una representación de la escala.

El grado de abstracción/concreción de una palabra se refiere al grado de especificidad de su contenido. Por ejemplo, la palabra "objeto" es poco concreta porque su contenido es compatible con una familia muy amplia y variada de objetos diferentes, mientras que la palabra "percha" es bastante concreta porque su contenido es compatible con una gama muy restringida de objetos. Valora las palabras en una escala de 1 a 9, siendo 1 "muy abstracto" y 9 "muy concreto".

We kindly ask you to indicate the level of valence, arousal and abstraction/concreteness of the concepts denoted by the following words.

Valence is the degree in which the concept refers to something that you feel that is negative (aversive) or positive (attractive). Rate the words on a scale of 1 to 9, with a score of 1 being “very negative” and 9 being “very positive”. Below you have a pictorial representation of the scale.

Arousal refers to the level of relaxation/excitation that the word generates. Use a scale of 1 to 9, with a score of 1 being “very low arousal” (something very relaxing/calming) and 9 “very high arousal” (the maximum level of excitement). Below you have a pictorial representation of the scale.

The level of abstraction/concreteness refers to the extent to which it has a specific content. For example, the word “object” has a low level of concreteness because its content can include a varied set of different objects. However, the word “hanger” has a high level of concreteness because its content can be applied to a very restricted set of objects. Make your rating using a scale of 1 to 9, with 1 being “very abstract” and 9 being “very concrete”.

- Instructions for the categorical ratings:

A continuación te pedimos que por favor puntúes cada una de las palabras en las 5 categorías emocionales que se presentan: alegría, ira, tristeza, miedo y asco.

Por favor, responde a todas las palabras del cuestionario marcando la puntuación que estimes en una escala de 1 a 5, siendo 1 “nada en absoluto” y 5 “extremadamente”.

No olvides responder a cada una de las categorías emocionales.

We kindly ask you to rate each of the following words according to the 5 emotional categories presented: happiness, anger, sadness, fear and disgust.

Please, answer to all of the words in the questionnaire by selecting the score that you consider appropriate on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being “nothing at all” and 5 “extremely”.

Do not forget to answer to each of the 5 emotional categories.